

Prospective evaluation of copy number alterations validates chromosome 1q gain as an independent marker of poor prognosis in localized Ewing sarcoma

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ewing sarcoma is a rare and aggressive tumor affecting mainly adolescents and young adults. Accurate risk stratification is critical for treatment tailoring, yet traditional clinical parameters lack sufficient predictive accuracy. While retrospective studies have identified potential molecular biomarkers, prospective validation is required for clinical implementation.

Methods: The international PROVABES consortium (PROspective Validation of Biomarkers in Ewing Sarcoma) aims to evaluate molecular prognostic markers in European patients treated under international phase III trials. This study focuses on copy number alterations (CNAs), in 305 primary tumors. Tissue microarrays were analyzed by FISH for chromosome 1q gain ($n = 297$) and 16q loss ($n = 266$). Genome-wide CNAs were further assessed using SNP arrays in 139 samples. Associations with clinical outcomes were evaluated via Kaplan-Meier and multivariate Cox regression, with event-free survival (EFS) and overall survival (OS) as endpoints.

Results: Chromosome 1q gain was significantly associated with shorter OS in both localized cases and the overall cohort, and with inferior EFS specifically in localized patients. In contrast, 16q loss showed no significant prognostic impact. Multivariate analysis confirmed 1q gain as an independent predictor of poor EFS in localized disease. Notably, a higher fraction of genome altered was associated with inferior OS and EFS not only in localized patients but also in the entire cohort, and remained an independent predictor of outcome despite the smaller subset analyzed.

Conclusions: This prospective study validates chromosome 1q gain as an independent marker of poor prognosis in localized Ewing sarcoma. Furthermore, the extent of genomic alteration emerges as a promising predictor of both OS and EFS. Incorporating these biomarkers may improve individualized risk stratification and ultimately enhance patient outcomes.

Abbreviations: Chr. 1qG, Gain of chromosome 1q; Chr. 16qL, Loss of chromosome 16q; Chr., Chromosome; CIN, Chromosomal INstability; CNA, Copy Number Alterations; EE2008, EWING 2008 trial; EE99, EURO-E.W.I.N.G 99 trial (EUROpean Ewing tumor Working Initiative of National Groups 1999); EFS, Event-Free Survival; EwS, Ewing Sarcoma; FFPE, Formalin-Fixed Paraffin-Embedded; FISH, Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization; HR, Hazard Ratio; OS, Overall Survival; PROVABES, PROspective Validation of Biomarkers in Ewing Sarcoma for personalized translational medicine; SNP_a, Single Nucleotide Polymorphism microarray; TMA, Tissue MicroArrays.

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1. Background

Ewing sarcoma (EwS) is an aggressive, poorly differentiated tumor of the bone and soft tissues, predominantly affecting children, adolescents, and young adults. With a worldwide incidence of $\sim 1.5/10^6$, it represents the second most common bone malignancy in the paediatric population (Grunewald et al., 2018; Dupuy et al., 2023). Despite advances in multimodal therapy—including high-intensity chemotherapy, surgery, and radiotherapy—survival rates have remained largely unchanged for over two decades. While two-thirds of the patients with localized disease achieve long-term remission, approximately 30 % relapse. Patients with primary disseminated disease (30 %) and those who relapse face a dismal prognosis, with a three-year event-free survival rate below 25 % (Grunewald et al., 2018; Bosma et al., 2019; Stahl et al., 2011). Clinical parameters such as primary dissemination, tumor site, size, patient age, and histological response to chemotherapy are currently established and used for risk stratification (Bosma et al., 2019). Patients are assigned to clinically defined, risk-adapted therapy strategies, however discrimination by these risk strata is limited and still continues to fail in too many patients (Shulman et al., 2022a). Even in the most favorable risk group, failure rates remain as high as 30 %, despite intensified treatment regimens. Moreover, current standard therapies expose young patients to severe long-term side effects, underscoring the urgent need for complementary risk models incorporating reliable molecular biomarkers. Identifying biological factors driving relapse and disease progression could refine risk stratification, distinguishing patients with localized disease at higher risk from those who may benefit from less intensive therapy. To enable accurate, risk-adapted treatment strategies, prospectively validated biomarkers are crucial (Shulman et al., 2022a).

The defining molecular hallmark of EwS are specific chromosomal translocations in which a member of the FET gene family fuses with an ETS transcription factor, generating oncogenic gene fusions, *EWSR1::FLII* in most of the cases, which are recognized as drivers of the disease and serve as molecular diagnostic criteria (Grunewald et al., 2018). EwS is classified as an undifferentiated small round-cell sarcoma (WHO Classification of Tumours Editorial Board, 2020), a group of neoplasms that also includes distinct entities molecularly defined by *EWSR1::non-ETS* fusions, CIC-rearrangements, and BCOR alterations (Cidre-Aranaz et al., 2022; Kallen and Hornick, 2021). There is a paucity of secondary recurrent mutations in EwS, which presents an exceptionally low mutation rate (Tirode et al., 2014; Crompton et al., 2014; Brohl et al., 2014; Grobner et al., 2018). Overall, tumor mutation burden in sarcomas is significantly lower than in carcinomas (Nacev et al., 2022), particularly in translocation-driven sarcomas subtypes (Gounder et al., 2022). In EwS, exceptions to this are *TP53*, mutated in 5–7 % of cases, and the cohesin complex family member *STAG2*, mutated in 15–21 % of cases (Tirode et al., 2014; Crompton et al., 2014; Brohl et al., 2014). Although EwS has traditionally been regarded as a tumor with a stable genome, several studies have identified recurrent genomic copy number alterations (CNAs). The relevance of chromosome 1q gain (chr. 1qG) as negative prognostic CNA in this neoplasm was described by our group and others (Tirode et al., 2014; Mackintosh et al., 2012; Hattinger et al., 2002). In a retrospective analysis of 67 EwS patient samples from a EURO EWING study, we demonstrated that chr. 1qG, detected in 30 % of tumors, was an independent predictor of poor prognosis, as confirmed by Cox regression analysis (Mackintosh et al., 2012). Other specific CNAs, such as loss of chromosome 16q (chr. 16qL) (Tirode et al., 2014; Hattinger et al., 2002; Ozaki et al., 2001) and *CDKN2A* microdeletion (Kovar et al., 2003; Huang et al., 2005), have also been linked to poor outcomes in EwS. Furthermore, our prior work demonstrated a strong correlation between overall CNA burden and patient prognosis (Mackintosh et al., 2012). The genome-wide CNA tumor profile, encompassing both chromosomal aneuploidies and sub-chromosomal structural alterations, reflects the degree of chromosomal instability (CIN)—a phenomenon increasingly recognized as a hallmark of cancer

evolution (Taluri et al., 2023) (Hanahan and Weinberg, 2011). CIN is known to have prognostic significance across multiple cancer types (Tijhuis et al., 2019). Consistent with this, our previous study revealed that a higher percentage of genome affected by CNAs was associated with progressively worse survival outcomes (Mackintosh et al., 2012). Other reports have similarly shown that an increased total number of CNAs appears to be a strong predictor of prognosis (Ozaki et al., 2001; Savola et al., 2009; Ferreira et al., 2008; Jahromi et al., 2012). In addition, G-banding karyotype studies have associated higher chromosomal complexity with poorer outcomes in EwS (Roberts et al., 2008; Zielenska et al., 2001).

While these retrospective studies have identified promising CNA biomarkers associated with aggressive disease, their clinical implementation requires rigorous prospective validation. To address this gap, the three leading investigator-driven European EwS study groups, EURO-EWING, the Italian Sarcoma Group (ISG), and the Spanish Sarcoma Group (GEIS) assembled a supranational consortium, PROVABES, for the PROspective VALidation of Biomarkers in EwS. Most European EwS patients are treated within clinical trials under the auspices of the clinical trial groups cooperating in this consortium. This ensures a homogenous cohort of patients in terms of treatment regimen, follow up and clinicopathological assessment. Within this joint framework, we analyzed a large cohort of patient-derived EwS samples to systematically evaluate the prognostic impact of chr.1qG and chr.16qL, with a particular focus on patients with localized disease, using a simple and cost-effective approach such as FISH (fluorescence in situ hybridization), which is available in most surgical pathology laboratories. In addition, we performed CNA profiling in a subset of samples using single nucleotide polymorphism arrays (SNPa) to assess their feasibility as a clinical tool and to evaluate the impact of genome-wide CNA burden on patient outcomes.

2. Methods

2.1. Study population and sample collection

This study was conceived as a coordinated effort of the three major European EwS trial groups that set up the PROVABES consortium. The primary aim of PROVABES is to validate selected biomarkers in EwS in a prospective joint investigational program. This concerted action approach allowed the reliable collection of clinical data and biomaterial from newly diagnosed EwS patients in Europe. Therefore, a common data set of precisely described EwS was retrieved with homogeneous clinical data. This work was performed as an ancillary study to the phase III clinical trials EWING 2008 (EE2008, EudraCT 2008–003658, NCT00987636), and EURO-E.W.I.N.G 99 (EE99, EUROpean Ewing tumor Working Initiative of National Groups Ewing Tumor Studies 1999, NCT00020566). Details on the respective trials are outlined on clinicaltrials.gov, clinicaltrialsregister.eu, and the International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number Register (ISRCTNR; controlled-trials.com). The clinical trials were approved by competent regulatory authorities in compliance with EU and national regulations. Informed consent documents were amended to include specific consent for participation in PROVABES.

Patients included in the PROVABES analysis met the following criteria: registration in the European phase III clinical trials participating in this consortium, fulfillment inclusion and exclusion criteria according to the respective trial protocol (including confirmed reference diagnosis of EwS), availability of tumor biomaterial, and informed consent for biomaterial collection. Since participation in phase III clinical trials represents the standard of care for newly diagnosed EwS patients in Europe, patient registration was population-based. All patients were treated according to the trial protocols, with the aim to administer induction chemotherapy followed by local treatment of the primary tumor. After local treatment, patients received maintenance therapy. Local pathologists assessed histological response after induction therapy

on the surgical specimen. Histological response was assessed by the degree of necrosis and was defined as poor when $\geq 10\%$ viable tumor cells were present.

A series of 305 EwS primary samples were prospectively collected from patients enrolled in the EE99 (48 samples) and EE2008 (257 samples) trials. Data processing was performed in accordance with the applicable data protection legislation and was supervised by institutional review boards. Clinical data acquisition, processing, and analysis were conducted by the international CESS trial center in Münster, which oversaw data management. The coordinating trial office merged the prospectively collected clinical data supplied by the participating groups according to common standardized operating procedures (SOPs). Tumor material was prospectively collected from cooperating national and international biobanks (TranSaRNet <http://transarnet.uni-muenster.de>, EuroBoNet, www.eurobonet.eu/CONTICANET www.conticanet.eu), using PROVABES-specific SOPs. Formalin-fixed, paraffin embedded (FFPE) tumor slides for genomic DNA extraction and tissue microarrays (TMA) for FISH probing were provided to the corresponding biobanks by the reference pathologists in each trial.

2.2. Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH)

Tumor paraffin sections included in TMAs were hybridized for FISH analyses using the following commercial probes: ZytoLight® SPEC MDM4/1p12 Dual Color Probe (ZytoVision), and ST 16qter (red) / ST 16pter (green) (KREATECH Diagnostics®). FISH assessment and interpretation were performed according to previously published procedures (Piqueras et al., 2011). Briefly, a minimum of 100 non-overlapping nuclei per core were evaluated. Multiple focal planes were analyzed to ensure the accurate detection of all hybridization signals. Control tissues (normal kidney, liver and placenta) incorporated in the TMA were used to account for cutting artifacts that can influence interphase FISH signal interpretation. Based on FISH signal patterns, we defined four groups:

- (1) No genetic alteration: Equal number of signals for the target and control chromosomal regions (1q = 1p; 16q = 16p).
- (2) Possible chr.1qG and/or chr.16qL: Unequal number of signals between the target (1q or 16q) and control probes (1p or 16p).
- (3) Cutting artifacts: Nuclei fragments generated during tissue sectioning, leading to signal discrepancies.
- (4) Confirmed chr.1qG and/or chr.16qL: The proportion of cells in Group 2, after subtracting those classified as artifacts (Group 3).

To define a threshold for genetic alterations, we set the mean + 3 standard deviations (SD) in Group 4 at $\leq 15\%$ for control tissues. The same scoring criteria were applied to tumor samples, where a genetic alteration was considered present when $>15\%$ of tumor cells fell into Group 4. TMA sections were independently evaluated for each genetic marker by two authors (MBM. and RN.) to ensure reproducibility.

2.3. Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Microarray (SNPa)

FFPE 10 μ sections were used to isolate genomic DNA using QIAamp DNA FFPE Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). DNA concentration was determined with Quant-iT™ PicoGreen dsDNA assay (Invitrogen, Waltham, Massachusetts, US) before genome-wide CNA analysis with molecular inversion probe SNP-based arrays (OncoScan FFPE Assay Kit, Thermo Fisher Scientific), as previously described (Rodriguez-Nunez et al., 2020). After scanning the arrays, CEL files were used to generate OSCHP files with the TuScan algorithm that uses B-allele frequencies (BAFs) and log₂ ratios to estimate the ploidy and percentage of aberrant cells in the sample, which in turn are used to calculate copy number calls. Visualization of OSCHP files and population-level analyses of CNA was performed with Nexus Copy Number v10 software (Bionano Genomics). CNA profile differences between event cases vs. censored cases and deceased vs. surviving patients were assessed using Fishers Exact

test within Nexus Copy Number v10 software (Bionano Genomics), to determine the likelihood of having so many events in one group vs. having a different number of the same events in the other group based on random chance. Differential threshold was set to 10 % and *p*-value to <0.05 . We used the survival predictive power tool (Nexus Copy Number v10 software, Bionano Genomics) to look for correlations between genomic alterations (e.g. gain/loss) across the entire genome and survival time, applying log-rank statistics.

2.4. Statistics

The primary endpoint, event-free survival (EFS), and the secondary endpoint, overall survival (OS), were estimated according to the method of Kaplan-Meier, and the differences in survival were evaluated using the log-rank test. EFS was defined as the time from diagnosis to the first event, including disease progression, relapse, secondary malignancy diagnosis, or death from any cause. Patients without an event were censored at the date of their last recorded consultation. Progression of disease was defined as recurrent disease occurring under active oncological therapy. Relapse of disease was defined as recurrent disease in patients who had achieved complete clinical remission after completing active oncological therapy. OS was defined as the time from diagnosis to death from any cause or the last known consultation. Patients lost to follow-up were censored at their last consultation date.

Associations between chromosomal alterations and clinicopathological characteristics were assessed using Fisher's exact test for the categorical variables. Differences in the continuous variable age were analyzed using the Mann-Whitney *U* test. Survival curves were estimated using the Kaplan-Meier method, and the differences in survival were evaluated using the log-rank test. The mean and median values of the Kaplan-Meier estimates are provided in Supplementary Table 1. Cox proportional hazards regression was used to estimate hazard ratios (HRs) and 95 % confidence intervals (CIs) for factors potentially associated with survival. Both crude and adjusted HRs were calculated to assess the impact of prognostic variables. For all comparisons, a two-tailed *p* value < 0.05 was considered to be relevant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS v20 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Prospective evaluation of chr.1qG and chr.16qL alterations as prognostic markers in EwS

Previous retrospective studies identified chr.1qG and chr.16qL as two of the most frequent CNAs associated with poor prognosis in EwS (Tirode et al., 2014; Mackintosh et al., 2012; Hattinger et al., 2002; Ozaki et al., 2001; Brisset et al., 2001). To validate these findings in a prospective setting, we evaluated chr.1qG and chr.16qL as potential prognostic markers for patient stratification, with a particular focus on those with localized disease at diagnosis. A total of 305 EwS samples were collected from patients enrolled in the EE99 ($n = 48$) and EE2008 ($n = 257$) clinical trials. Baseline characteristics at diagnosis are summarized in Table 1. Among the 305 cases, 207 had localized disease at diagnosis, and 98 presented with metastatic disease. FISH assays were performed to assess chr.1qG and chr.16qL in 297 and 266 primary tumor samples, respectively. SNPa analysis was conducted in a subset of 139 samples as an untargeted exploratory approach to identify other potential CNAs influencing patient prognosis. A small number of cases were analyzed exclusively by SNPa: 12 cases with SNPa data lacked FISH data for chr.16q, and 3 cases with SNPa data lacked FISH data for chr.1q. A summary of sample allocation, molecular assays, and subsequent analyses is provided in Supplementary Fig. 1.

The frequency of cases presenting chr.1qG in the entire series was 11.7 % (35/300). When considering only patients with localized disease, the frequency of chr.1qG decreased slightly to 10.8 % (22/204). A similar trend was observed for chr.16qL, with a marginally lower

Table 1
Patient demographics at diagnosis. Age is presented by mean along with corresponding standard deviation (SD) between brackets, while categorical variables are expressed as counts and percentages (%).

	Analyzable
Study enrolment	305
EE99	48 (15.7 %)
EE2008	257 (84.3 %)
Age (mean, years + SD)	305
	17.59 (9.91)
Gender	305
Male	175 (57.4 %)
Female	130 (42.6 %)
Histologic response	205
Good	164 (80 %)
Poor	41 (20 %)
Tumor vol.	267
<200 ml	157 (58.8 %)
≥200 ml	110 (41.2 %)
Pelvic location	305
No	244 (80 %)
Yes	61 (20 %)
Disease extent	305
Localized	207 (67.9 %)
Metastatic	98 (32.1 %)

frequency among localized cases (10.4 %, 19/183) compared to the entire cohort (11.9 %, 33/278). Overall, the frequencies of chr.1qG and chr.16qL in our study were lower than those reported in prior studies.

Previous studies have reported that chr.1qG and chr.16qL frequently occur concurrently, possibly as a consequence of an unbalanced translocation between these two chromosomes (Roberts et al., 2008; Hattinger et al., 1996). In our cohort, we confirmed the co-occurrence of both alterations in 12 cases accounting for 12/35 (34.3 %) of 1qG-positive cases and 12/32 (37.5 %) of 16qL-positive cases, significantly more than expected by chance ($p < 0.001$, Fisher exact test, Table 2).

3.2. Clinical and pathologic findings according to genomic alterations

Analysis of the compiled data revealed no relevant differences in gender or mean age between patients with the alterations chr.1qG or chr.16qL, and those without, both in the localized tumors series and in the entire cohort (Tables 3 and 4). In localized tumors chr.1qG was associated with pelvic tumor location, events, and exitus (patient deceased) (Table 3), but showed no correlation with histological response or tumor volume. In the whole series, the association between chr.1qG and events and exitus was not statistically significant, although its frequency remained higher among patients experiencing events (15.7 % vs. 9.2 %) or death (17.5 % vs. 9.5 %) (Table 4). For chr.16qL, the only relevant finding was its association with poor histological response in localized tumors (Table 3). Neither chr.1qG nor chr.16qL showed an association with disease extent at diagnosis (Table 4).

We next evaluated the impact of the genomic alterations chr.1qG and

Table 2
 Co-occurrence of chr. 1qG and 16qL in EwS samples.

		Chr. 16q Loss		Total
		negative	positive	
Chr. 1q Gain	Negative	218	20	238
	Positive	23	12	35
	Total	241	32	273

chr.16qL on patient survival time. Kaplan–Meier estimates showed that patients with chr.1qG-positive tumors had significantly shorter EFS in the localized tumor series (mean: 5.33 vs. 8.31 years, $p = 0.012$, Fig. 1A), although this association was not statistically significant in the overall cohort (mean: 4.83 vs. 7.19 years, $p = 0.071$, Fig. 1B). In contrast, chr.1qG status significantly influenced OS, with shorter survival times observed in both the localized tumors (mean: 6.23 vs. 9.87 years, $p = 0.008$, Fig. 1C) and the overall cohort (mean: 5.73 vs. 8.74 years, $p = 0.032$, Fig. 1D). For chr.16qL, a trend toward worse survival was noted, but differences did not reach statistical significance for any study endpoint in either localized or overall series (Fig. 1E–H). Given the frequent co-occurrence of chr.1qG and chr.16qL (Table 2), we evaluated their combination without observing an additional effect on survival (Supplementary Fig. 2).

Cox regression univariate analyses (Table 5) revealed that chr.1qG was correlated with both EFS and OS in the localized cohort, with unadjusted HRs of 2.353 ($p = 0.015$) and 3 ($p = 0.011$) respectively. Among clinical parameters, only age significantly influenced time to event. Since not all patients underwent surgical local treatment, histological response could be evaluated in only 157 cases. In multivariate analysis, chr.1qG remained an independent prognostic factor for EFS, even after adjusting for all four clinical variables (Table 5). By contrast, chr.16qL was not associated with either EFS or OS in the localized cohort according to the univariate Cox model (Table 5). Univariate and multivariate analyses were also performed for the overall cohort (Table 6). While chr.1qG was associated with OS in univariate analysis (HR = 1.864, $p = 0.03$), this association did not remain significant in the multivariate model (Table 6).

3.3. SNP analysis reveals the prognostic impact of genome-wide CNA profiles in EwS

We analyzed the genome-wide CNA profile in a subset of 139 samples with sufficient and suitable material for DNA extraction. Patient demographics and clinical parameters in this subset (Supplementary Table 2) were comparable to those of the full cohort (Table 1). FISH and SNP assays were highly concordant for detecting chr.1qG and chr.16qL (Table 7). Discordant cases corresponded to whole-chromosome alterations not detectable by the FISH probes, which target segmental changes. Specifically, two cases were negative for chr.1qG by FISH but showed whole chr.1 gain by SNP, and four cases were negative for chr.16qL by FISH but exhibited whole chr.16 loss by SNP.

SNP analyses revealed that genomic gains were more frequent than losses, identifying recurrent CNAs consistent with previous studies (Tirode et al., 2014; Mackintosh et al., 2012; Savola et al., 2009) (Fig. 2). The most common CNA was whole chr.8 gain (43.9 %), followed by less frequent gains of chr.1q (12.2 %) and whole chromosomes 2, 5, 12, 14, and 20. Recurrent losses included chr.10 (10 %) and chr.16q (12.2 %), along with microdeletions at 9p21.3 involving the CDKN2A locus (14.4 %) which frequently extended to the adjacent locus CDKN2B (Supplementary Fig. 3).

Previous studies, including our own, have suggested that the fraction of the genome affected by CNAs is associated with poor outcomes in EwS (Mackintosh et al., 2012; Tirode et al., 2014). To further explore this, we analyzed the percentage of genome altered (PGA) in the subset of 139 EwS cases and correlated it with clinical parameters. Cases were categorized as low-PGA or high-PGA using the median value as cutoff. Interestingly, high-PGA cases were significantly associated with poor histological response and pelvic tumor localization in both the localized and overall cohorts, whereas no association was observed with tumor volume. Patients who experienced an event or death were more frequently classified as high-PGA in both cohorts. Moreover, high-PGA patients tended to be older, though this correlation was significant only in the whole cohort (Table 8).

Kaplan–Meyer estimates demonstrated that high-PGA cases had an unfavorable prognosis for both EFS and OS (Fig. 3 and Supplementary

Table 3

Clinical and pathological findings in the series of patients with localized tumors at diagnosis according to the genomic alterations chr.1qG and chr.16qL. SD, standard deviation.

Characteristics	Analyzable	Chr.1q			p	Analyzable	Chr.16q		p
		Neutral (182)	Gain (22)				Neutral (164)	Loss (19)	
Age, years mean (SD)	204	17.93 (±10.45)	22.03 (±13.87)	0.343	183	18.83 (±10.98)	17.67 (±12.38)	0.375	
Gender	204			1	183			0.330	
Male	114	102 (89.5 %)	12 (10.5 %)		102	89 (87.3 %)	13 (12.7 %)		
Female	90	80 (88.9 %)	10 (11.1 %)		81	75 (92.6 %)	6 (7.4 %)		
Histologic response	156			1	136			0.038	
Good	126	114 (90.5 %)	12 (9.5 %)		112	102 (91.1 %)	10 (8.9 %)		
Poor	30	27 (90 %)	3 (10 %)		24	18 (75 %)	6 (25 %)		
Tumor Vol.	175			0.078	158			0.596	
<200 ml	155	109 (91.6 %)	10 (8.4 %)		103	93 (90.3 %)	10 (9.7 %)		
≥ 200 ml	20	46 (82.1 %)	10 (17.9 %)		55	48 (87.3 %)	7 (12.7 %)		
Pelvic location	204			0.003	183			0.345	
No	171	158 (92.4 %)	13 (7.6 %)		150	136 (90.7 %)	14 (9.3 %)		
Yes	33	24 (72.7 %)	9 (27.3 %)		33	28 (84.8 %)	5 (15.2 %)		
Event	204			0.038	183			0.788	
No	151	139 (92.1 %)	12 (7.9 %)		132	119 (90.2 %)	13 (9.8 %)		
Yes	53	43 (81.1 %)	10 (18.9 %)		51	45 (88.2 %)	6 (11.8 %)		
Exitus	204			0.025	183			0.088	
No	174	159 (91.4 %)	15 (8.6 %)		154	141 (91.6 %)	13 (8.4 %)		
Yes	30	23 (76.7 %)	7 (23.3 %)		29	23 (79.3 %)	6 (20.7 %)		

Table 4

Clinical and pathological findings in the whole series (localized and metastatic) according to the genomic alterations chr.1qG and chr.16qL. SD, standard deviation.

Characteristics	Analyzable	Chr.1q			p	Analyzable	Chr.16q		p
		Neutral (265)	Gain (35)				Neutral (245)	Loss (33)	
Age, years mean (SD)	300	17.49 (±9.58)	19.30 (±12.47)	0.753	278	18.00 (±10.01)	16.75 (±10.58)	0.365	
Gender	300			0.721	278			0.852	
Male	171	152 (88.9 %)	19 (11.1 %)		160	140 (87.5 %)	20 (12.5 %)		
Female	129	113 (87.6 %)	16 (12.4 %)		118	105 (89 %)	13 (11 %)		
Histologic response	204			1	181			0.39	
Good	163	147 (90.2 %)	16 (9.8 %)		147	130 (88.4 %)	17 (11.6 %)		
Poor	41	37 (90.2 %)	4 (9.8 %)		34	28 (82.4 %)	6 (17.6 %)		
Tumor Vol.	262			0.129	244			0.335	
<200 ml	154	139 (90.3 %)	15 (9.7 %)		139	124 (89.2 %)	15 (10.8 %)		
≥ 200 ml	108	90 (83.3 %)	18 (16.7 %)		105	89 (84.8 %)	16 (15.2 %)		
Pelvic location	300			0.003	278			0.376	
No	241	220 (91.3 %)	21 (8.7 %)		218	194 (89 %)	24 (11 %)		
Yes	59	45 (76.3 %)	14 (23.7 %)		60	51 (85 %)	9 (15 %)		
Disease extent	300			0.488	278			0.287	
Localized	204	182 (89.2 %)	22 (10.8 %)		183	164 (89.6 %)	19 (10.4 %)		
Metastatic	96	83 (86.5 %)	13 (13.5 %)		95	81 (85.3 %)	14 (14.7 %)		
Event	300			0.099	278			0.573	
No	185	168 (90.8 %)	17 (9.2 %)		166	148 (89.2 %)	18 (10.8 %)		
Yes	115	97 (84.3 %)	18 (15.7 %)		112	97 (86.6 %)	15 (13.4 %)		
Exitus	300			0.068	278			0.148	
No	220	199 (90.5 %)	21 (9.5 %)		200	180 (90 %)	20 (10 %)		
Yes	80	66 (82.5 %)	14 (17.5 %)		78	65 (83.3 %)	13 (16.7 %)		

Fig. 4). Cox analyses further identified increased PGA as an independent prognostic factor significantly associated with EFS, both in patients with localized disease (Table 9), and in the overall cohort including metastatic cases at diagnosis (Table 10). PGA also emerged as an independent predictor of OS in the overall cohort, together with metastasis (Table 10). Notably, PGA and metastasis were the only two independent prognostic parameters across the overall cohort (Table 10).

Next, we compared CNA profile between tumors from patients who relapsed or progressed and those from patients without events, as well as between tumors from patients with fatal outcomes and those alive at the last follow-up. Gains in chr.1q, particularly in the proximal region, were more frequent in patients with unfavorable outcomes (Fig. 4). In addition, chr.16qL was enriched in tumors from patients with fatal outcomes (Fig. 4C, D).

Additionally, we identified other CNAs associated with poor prognosis. Losses on chr.10 and gains on chr.2 and 20 were consistently more frequent in patients with adverse outcomes across all comparisons. Some

alterations, however, were enriched only in localized tumors. Notably, microdeletion of the *CDKN2A* locus at cytoband 9p21.3 emerged as a recurrent alteration in tumors from patients with poor outcomes in all comparisons (Fig. 4).

We next utilized the “survival predictive power” tool (described in the Methods section) to perform an untargeted exploratory analysis aimed at identifying CNAs across the entire genome that may influence patient survival time within the subset of 139 patients. This analysis revealed that gains in chr.1q, chr.2q, *CDKN2A/B* microdeletions, and losses in chr.10 (typically involving the entire chromosome) and in chr.16q were significantly associated with worse OS (Supplementary Table 3). Similarly, all those alterations, except chr.16q loss, were also associated to shorter EFS (Supplementary Table 4). Interestingly, two cases with chr.10 losses exhibited homozygous deletions of *PTEN* (Supplementary Fig. 5).

Fig. 1. Kaplan–Meier curves for EFS and OS in EwS patients, stratified by chr. 1qG and 16qL status.

4. Discussion

Numerous host, disease, and environmental factors contribute to substantial clinical heterogeneity in diagnosis, treatment, and outcomes, thereby complicating the discovery and validation of reliable biomarkers. To address these challenges, PROVABES was conceived as an integrative approach to analyse biomarkers using prospectively collected material from comprehensively documented patients treated under standardized protocols. In this controlled setting, our study demonstrates, in a large cohort, that chr.1qG is an independent marker of poor prognosis in EwS patients with localized disease, after adjusting for established clinical factors. In contrast, chr.16qL could not be validated as a prognostic marker. Importantly, the prognostic relevance of chr.1qG in patients with localized disease provides additional

discriminatory value beyond clinical factors. In multivariate analyses, some associations observed in univariate tests were attenuated in the whole cohort after adjusting for clinical variables, most notably the presence of metastasis, which remains the strongest predictor of outcome.

The frequencies of chr.1qG and chr.16qL as observed with FISH or SNPs in our cohort are lower than in previous reports. Differences in the reported frequencies are unlikely to reflect reduced sensitivity of our approach, as FISH has sufficient resolution to detect chr.1qG and chr.16qL, and the SNPs employed have resolution equal to or higher than that of karyotyping or CGH arrays used in previous studies. A more plausible explanation lies in the prospective design of our study, which excluded post-treatment material, whereas many retrospective studies do not specify whether tumors had been previously treated. Treatment

Table 5
Univariate and multivariate Cox regression models assessing the impact of chr.1qG and 16qL on EFS and OS in patients with localized EWS.

Factors	Time to event						Overall survival											
	Univariate			Multivariate 1			Multivariate 2			Univariate			Multivariate 1			Multivariate 2		
	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P
Chr. 1q status (Gain vs Normal)	203	2.353 (1.179-4.699)	0.015	203	2.364 (1.183-4.721)	0.02	132	2.731 (1.167-6.392)	0.021	203	3.000 (1.281-7.026)	0.011	174	2.349 (0.928-5.945)	0.072	132	2.822 (0.890-8.952)	0.078
Chr.16q status (Loss vs Normal)	182	1.236 (0.526-2.902)	0.627				182	2.384 (0.970-5.860)		182	2.384 (0.970-5.860)	0.058				132	2.604 (0.972-6.980)	0.057
Histological response (good vs. poor)	157	1.985 (0.991-3.977)	0.053				132	1.095 (0.444-2.700)	0.843	157	4.083 (1.763-9.454)	0.001				132	2.604 (0.972-6.980)	0.057
Tumor volume (<200 ml vs. ≥ 200 ml)	177	1.561 (0.859-2.837)	0.144				132	1.358 (0.657-2.808)	0.408	177	2.391 (1.106-5.171)	0.027	174	2.281 (1.043-4.989)	0.039	132	1.714 (0.657-4.471)	0.271
Pelvic location	206	1.542 (0.790-3.007)	0.204				132	1.386 (0.562-3.418)	0.479	206	1.477 (0.600-3.638)	0.396						
Age (≥16 vs. < 16 years)	206	1.911 (1.099-3.323)	0.022	203	1.844 (1.061-3.206)	0.03	132	2.381 (1.152-4.920)	0.019	206	1.215 (0.592-2.491)	0.596						
Gender (male vs female)	206	1.365 (0.794-2.346)	0.261				206	1.301 (0.632-2.677)		206	1.301 (0.632-2.677)	0.476						

Table 6
Univariate and multivariate Cox regression models assessing the impact of chr.1qG and 16qL on EFS and OS in patients with localized and metastatic EWS.

Factors	Time to event						Overall survival											
	Univariate			Multivariate 1			Multivariate 2			Univariate			Multivariate 1			Multivariate 2		
	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	P	Anal.	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	P
Chr. 1q status (Gain vs Normal)	298	1.584 (0.957-2.623)	0.074	261	1.355 (0.799-2.298)	0.259	175	1.934 (0.926-4.041)	0.079	298	1.864 (1.046-3.324)	0.035	261	1.530 (0.835-2.803)	0.169	175	1.672 (0.678-4.120)	0.264
Chr.16q status (Loss vs Normal)	276	1.267 (0.735-2.183)	0.394				276	1.505 (0.829-2.731)		276	1.505 (0.829-2.731)	0.179						
Disease extent (metastatic vs localized)	303	3.778 (2.611-5.468)	>0.001	261	3.209 (2.111-4.878)	>0.001	175	2.189 (1.216-3.942)	0.009	303	4.883 (3.099-7.695)	>0.001	261	3.954 (2.376-6.580)	>0.001	175	3.211 (1.597-6.456)	0.001
Histological response (good vs. poor)	205	2.263 (1.332-3.872)	0.003				175	1.651 (0.876-3.112)	0.121	205	3.868 (2.097-7.137)	>0.001				175	3.067 (1.538-6.115)	0.001
Tumor volume (<200 ml vs. ≥ 200 ml)	266	1.858 (1.259-2.744)	0.002	261	1.336 (0.878-2.033)	0.177	175	1.204 (0.675-2.147)	0.529	266	2.450 (1.532-3.921)	>0.001	261	1.691 (1.015-2.817)	0.044	175	1.644 (0.798-3.389)	0.178
Pelvic location	303	1.616 (1.065-2.454)	0.024	261	1.124 (0.701-1.804)	0.627	175	1.107 (0.514-2.383)	0.795	303	1.614 (0.988-2.636)	0.056	261	0.942 (0.541-1.642)	0.833	175	0.716 (0.248-2.068)	0.537
Age (<16 vs. ≥ 16 years)	303	1.301 (0.903-1.874)	0.158	261	1.116 (0.752-1.657)	0.586	175	1.555 (0.894-2.702)	0.118	303	1.104 (0.714-1.707)	0.657						
Gender (male vs female)	303	1.101 (0.763-1.588)	0.607				303	0.964 (0.620-1.498)		303	0.964 (0.620-1.498)	0.870						

Table 7
Comparison of FISH and SNPa results for chr.1qG and chr.16qL.

		SNPa	
		Negative	Positive
FISH chr.1qG	Negative	120 (98.4 %)	2 (1.6 %)
	Positive	0 (0 %)	14 (100 %)
FISH chr.16qL	Negative	110 (96.5 %)	4 (3.5 %)
	Positive	0 (0 %)	13 (100 %)

regimens have been associated with increased genomic instability, and chr.1qG has been shown to occur more frequently in treated samples (50 %) than in diagnostic samples (14 %) (Crompton et al., 2014), supporting the notion that prospective diagnostic cohorts provide a more accurate baseline profile. In addition, the clinical management of patients in our series was more homogeneous than in retrospective reports, which may be biased toward cases with poorer outcomes that undergo more extensive molecular testing. For instance, Tirode et al. reported chr.1qG in 19 % of cases in a cohort with a higher rate of fatal outcomes (36.9 % vs. 26.6 % in our series), while Roberts et al. (Roberts et al., 2008) described chr.1qG in 16 % of cases by karyotyping in a series with 34 % fatal outcomes.

Chr.1qG is a common recurrent alteration observed across diverse types of cancer with distinct genomic profiles and has been reported as an early event strongly associated with disease progression (Girish et al.,

2023). Chromosome gains have been deemed as a mechanism to increase the dosage of tumor-promoting genes located within the affected regions (Davoli et al., 2013). Our group previously reported that transcriptomic profiling of 1qG EwS revealed severe cell cycle deregulation that could be partially attributed to overexpression of *CDT2* (located at 1q32.3), a gene encoding a protein involved in ubiquitin ligase activity and significantly overexpressed in chr.1qG EwS tumors. *CDT2* is the main substrate receptor of the ubiquitin ligase complex CUL4/DDB1, and we described that *CDT2* knockdown induces dramatic changes in the protein levels of several G1 to S transition inhibitors that are known specific targets of that complex, establishing it as a strong contributor to enhanced proliferative capacity and poor prognosis (Mackintosh et al., 2012). However, the potential contribution of other chr.1q prominent candidates cannot be overlooked, since no genomic amplifications centered on the *CDT2* locus were detected, and nearly one-third of chr.1q genes showed expression shifts due to this CNA (Mackintosh et al., 2012). Notably, in addition to *CDT2*, this study also identified other candidate genes on chromosome 1q for which we have subsequently demonstrated functional relevance in EwS, including *PARP1* and *DHX9* (Ordonez et al., 2015; Olmedo-Pelayo et al., 2025).

Chromosome-scale alterations can affect hundreds of genes simultaneously, and thus the functional effect of arm-length aneuploidy may rely on multiple functionally interacting loci that collectively confer oncogenic properties (Bonney et al., 2015). The novel concept of oncogene-like addition to aneuploidy has been proposed to account for

Fig. 2. Summary of the CNAs detected in 139 EwS samples. Frequencies of copy number gain (above the axis, blue) and copy number loss (below the axis, red) across the entire genome are shown as detected with OncoScan SNPa. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 8
Clinical and pathological findings according to the percentage of the altered genome (PGA). SD, standard deviation.

Characteristics	Analyzable	LOCALIZED CASES			WHOLE SERIES			
		PGA (median cutoff)		p	Analyzable	PGA (median cutoff)		p
		Low % (48)	High % (47)			Low % (70)	High % (69)	
Age, years mean (SD)	95	19.88 (±9.85)	24.39 (±11.86)	0.051	139	19.35 (±9.19)	23.11 (±10.88)	0.033
Gender	95			0.683	139			0.605
Male	55	30 (54.5 %)	25 (45.5 %)		83	40 (48.2 %)	43 (51.8 %)	
Female	40	20 (50 %)	20 (50 %)		56	30 (53.6 %)	26 (46.4 %)	
Histologic response	75			0.025	97			0.027
Good	64	36 (56.3 %)	28 (43.8 %)		82	48 (58.5 %)	34 (41.5 %)	
Poor	11	2 (18.2 %)	9 (81.8 %)		15	4 (26.7 %)	11 (73.3 %)	
Tumor Vol.	78			0.637	115			0.914
<200 ml	50	26 (52 %)	24 (48 %)		66	33 (50 %)	33 (50 %)	
≥ 200 ml	28	13 (46.4 %)	15 (53.6 %)		49	25 (51 %)	24 (49 %)	
Pelvic location	95			0.002	139			< 0.001
No	77	45 (58.4 %)	32 (41.6 %)		107	63 (58.9 %)	44 (41.1 %)	
Yes	18	3 (16.7 %)	15 (83.3 %)		32	7 (21.9 %)	25 (78.1 %)	
Event	95			0.001	139			0.003
No	67	41 (61.2 %)	26 (38.8 %)		82	50 (61 %)	32 (39 %)	
Yes	28	7 (25 %)	21 (75 %)		57	20 (35.1 %)	37 (64.9 %)	
Exitus	95			0.04	139			0.003
No	82	45 (54.9 %)	37 (45.1 %)		102	59 (57.8 %)	43 (42.2 %)	
Yes	13	3 (23.1 %)	10 (76.9 %)		37	11 (29.7 %)	26 (70.3 %)	
Disease extent					139			0.431
Localized					95	50	45	
Metastatic					44	20	24	

Fig. 3. Kaplan-Meier curves for EFS and OS in EwS patients stratified by percentage of genome altered (PGA, median cut-off).

this phenomenon. Recently, genomic editing using CRISPR-based chromosome engineering tools to generate isogenic cancer cell line models of aneuploidy, revealed that eliminating the chr.1q trisomy abolished anchorage-independent growth and xenograft formation, while upregulating p53 target genes in *TP53* wild-type cell lines. Oncogene-like addiction to chr.1q trisomy seemed to be centered around the activity of *MDM4* in suppressing p53 signaling (Girish et al., 2023). However, mutations in *TP53* and chr.1qG do not appear to be mutually exclusive in EwS (Tirode et al., 2014; Crompton et al., 2014). Interestingly, chr.1q trisomy addition also creates collateral therapeutic vulnerabilities, as 1q-trisomic cell lines displayed enhanced sensitivity to the nucleotide analogs RX-3117 and 3-deazauridine, attributable to the overexpression of the nucleotide kinase *UCK2* (Girish et al., 2023).

Regarding additional CNA alterations, our exploratory genome-wide profiling of 139 samples confirmed the relevance of *CDKN2A* deletion (Tirode et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2005) and identified chr.10 loss as a novel prognostic marker. Previous studies may have overlooked this alteration due to smaller sample sizes. In our previous work using CGH arrays, we did observe a marginal association between chr.10 loss and shorter disease-free survival but not with overall survival (Mackintosh et al., 2012). Overall, CNA profile in our series was consistent with previous reports (Tirode et al., 2014; Mackintosh et al., 2012; Savola et al., 2009). We also observed that increased PGA strongly associates with unfavorable patient outcomes. It remains unclear whether PGA alone or a combined index integrating multiple CNAs provides a better prognostic marker than single alterations. Indeed, we observed in this study that chr.1qG-positive cases exhibited a higher PGA (U Mann-Whitney test, $p = 0.000042$). Thus, PGA warrants further prospective evaluation in an extended series to fully validate its prognostic value, particularly in cases lacking chr.1qG.

Beyond CNAs, single nucleotide variants could be also incorporated as molecular prognostic markers in EwS. Despite EwS having a low mutational burden, landmark EwS genomic landscape studies have identified *STAG2* (15–20 %) and *TP53* (5–10 %) as recurrently mutated genes (Tirode et al., 2014; Crompton et al., 2014; Brohl et al., 2014). *STAG2*, a component of the cohesin complex involved in chromosomal stability and DNA repair, has emerged as particularly relevant: loss of *STAG2* protein expression — even in non-mutated cases, likely due to potential epigenetic silencing — is associated with worse survival outcomes independent of other clinical features, making it a strong

candidate for risk stratification (Shulman et al., 2022b). By contrast, the prognostic significance of *TP53* mutations remains controversial; however, concurrent mutation of *STAG2* and *TP53* strongly correlates with worse prognosis (Tirode et al., 2014). Integrating chr.1qG, *STAG2* loss of expression, and other molecular markers with strong evidence as reliable prognostic biomarkers into new stratification criteria would provide a stronger foundation for personalized treatment in EwS.

Attempts to enhance the predictive power of clinical factors have been made through merged indexes to build stratification schemes of prognostic groups of patients (Rodriguez-Galindo et al., 2007; Biswas et al., 2015; Karski et al., 2016). Recently, some of the authors of our present work developed survival estimation tools in EwS, both at diagnosis and after surgery. A diagnostic flowchart was proposed for patient stratification based on age, tumor volume, location, and disease extent, while a post-surgery flowchart incorporated histological response to guide treatment adjustments according to necrosis levels (Bosma et al., 2019). These tools show a fair predictive capability, thereby suitable for clinical use, but still leave ample room for improvement. The same applies to other earlier studies, which present limitations in the context of the contemporary treatment setting since patients in those studies were treated with outdated chemotherapy regimens. Moreover, eligibility criteria were primarily based on histologic diagnosis, and molecular testing largely restricted to *EWSR1* FISH probing, which cannot discriminate cases involving *EWSR1*-non ETS translocations (Shulman et al., 2022a). Currently, all patients receive multi-agent intensive chemotherapy and trial recruitment rely on next-generation sequencing methods that provide superior analytical sensitivity for accurately identifying the pathognomonic gene fusions (Salguero-Aranda et al., 2020; Salguero-Aranda and Diaz-Martín, 2021).

Effective implementation of molecular markers into routine clinical practice would provide valuable additional information to improve current stratification schemes, which are still based exclusively on clinical parameters. This goal would be facilitated by the use of testing methods affordable to any molecular pathology laboratory. Inexpensive and straightforward assays such as IHC determination for *STAG2* loss of expression (Shulman et al., 2022b), or FISH probing for chr.1qG would fulfill this requisite. Importantly, chr.1qG can be readily assessed by FISH on routine diagnostic samples, similar to the way FISH is currently used to confirm the pathognomonic translocation in centers with limited access to sequencing technologies, making its clinical implementation both feasible and immediately applicable. Refined risk stratification of

Table 9
Univariate and multivariable Cox regression models assessing the impact of PGA on EFS and OS in patients with localized EWS.

Factors	Time to relapse						Overall survival								
	Univariate			Multivariate 1			Univariate			Multivariate					
	Anal	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	p			
PGA (Low vs High)	94	3.549 (1.507-8.357)	0.004	75	2.895 (1.093-7.666)	0.032	75	2.738 (1.032-7.263)	0.043	94	3.600 (0.990-13.090)	0.052	75	2.221 (0.409-12.072)	0.356
Histological response (good vs. poor)	75	2.953 (1.121-7.780)	0.028	75	2.062 (0.745-5.710)	0.164	75	1.646 (0.572-4.734)	0.356	75	7.964 (2.049-30.960)	0.003	75	5.986 (1.391-25.755)	0.016
Tumor volume (<200 ml vs. ≥ 200 ml)	77	1.757 (0.726-4.248)	0.211							77	3.062 (0.861-10.892)	0.084			
Pelvic location	94	1.909 (0.801-4.550)	0.145							94	2.323 (0.698-7.729)	0.169			
Age (<16 vs. ≥ 16 years)	94	2.534 (0.961-6.681)	0.06				75	2.120 (0.683-6.579)	0.193	94	2.984 (0.658-13.530)	0.156			
Gender (male vs female)	94	1.276 (0.599-2.722)	0.528							94	0.929 (0.295-2.929)	0.900			

Table 10
Univariate and multivariable Cox regression models assessing the impact of PGA on EFS and OS in patients with localized and metastatic EWS.

Factors	Time to relapse						Overall survival											
	Univariate			Multivariate 1			Univariate			Multivariate 1			Multivariate 2					
	Anal	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Adj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	p	Anal	Unadj. HR (95 %CI)	p			
PGA (Low vs High)	137	2.243 (1.300-3.871)	0.003	97	2.474 (1.201-5.096)	0.014	137	2.077 (1.195-3.607)	0.009	137	2.668 (1.316-5.408)	0.006	97	4.461 (1.407-14.149)	0.011	137	2.482 (1.212-5.085)	0.013
Disease extent (metastatic vs localized)	137	3.491 (2.059-5.919)	>0.001	97	2.435 (1.165-5.091)	0.018	137	3.412 (2.005-5.806)	>0.001	137	5.441 (2.747-10.774)	>0.001	97	4.375 (1.626-11.769)	0.003	137	5.227 (2.628-10.399)	>0.001
Histological response (good vs. poor)	97	2.338 (1.046-5.228)	0.039	97	1.702 (0.739-3.916)	0.211				97	4.733 (1.775-12.620)	0.002	97	3.502 (1.301-9.427)	0.013			
Tumor volume (<200 ml vs. ≥ 200 ml)	114	1.467 (0.821-2.622)	0.196							114	1.997 (0.991-4.024)	0.053						
Pelvic location	137	1.632 (0.910-2.928)	0.1							137	1.864 (0.930-3.737)	0.079						
Age (<16 vs. ≥ 16 years)	137	2.095 (1.084-4.048)	0.028	97	1.764 (0.745-4.173)	0.197	137	1.808 (0.932-3.508)	0.08	137	2.086 (0.916-4.752)	0.08						
Gender (male vs female)	137	0.964 (0.567-1.683)	0.891							137	0.741 (0.375-1.463)	0.388						

Fig. 4. CNA profile comparisons. The upper section of each panel displays the frequency difference in CNA between the two groups being compared. Bars in this section highlight genomic regions with significant differences. Below, CNA frequencies across the genome are plotted for each group separately. (A) Localized tumor series, comparison of patients with adverse events vs event-free patients. (B) Localized and metastatic tumors, comparison of patients with adverse events vs event-free patients. (C) Localized tumors series, comparison of patients with fatal outcomes (exitus) vs patients alive at last follow-up. (D) Localized and metastatic tumors, comparison of patients with fatal outcomes (exitus) vs patients alive at last follow-up.

patients will enhance treatment personalization, enabling early intervention in high-risk patients while reducing treatment intensity and the associated treatment-induced long-term morbidity in lower-risk groups, ultimately improving both patient outcomes and quality of life.

Our study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, although this represents one of the largest prospective cohorts of Ewing sarcoma patients analyzed to date, the number of cases with available SNP data was still moderate, which may have limited the statistical power for some subgroup analyses. This was mainly due to limited availability of tumor material and the poor DNA yield obtained from some FFPE samples with variable preservation quality. Second, FISH assays were performed on tissue punches embedded in TMAs. While this approach enables high-throughput analysis, it may not fully capture intratumoral heterogeneity of the CNAs assessed. Finally, although patients were treated under harmonized international clinical trial protocols, subtle differences in management across participating centers cannot be entirely excluded.

5. Conclusion

Chr.1qG emerges as an additional biomarker to refine risk stratification in patients with localized EwS at diagnosis, a setting where clinical variables alone provide limited discriminatory power. The prospective validation of chr.1qG as a reliable prognostic marker in localized EwS offers compelling evidence to support its inclusion in risk classification models. Integrating chr.1qG or PGA, and other prognostic molecular biomarkers alongside clinical parameters will allow building more robust stratification criteria that can ad hoc be implemented into European treatment strategies and protocols. This will empower clinicians with reliable predictors to guide risk-adapted therapy strategies, ultimately improving EwS patient management and outcomes.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study as part of the Euro-E.W.I.N.G.99 ([ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00020566) identifier: NCT00020566) and EWING 2008 clinical trials ([ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00987636) identifier: NCT00987636).

Consent for publication

All the authors reviewed and accepted the contents of the article.

Availability of data and materials

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors on request.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Juan Díaz-Martín: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andreas Ranft:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maite Blanquer-Maceiras:** Investigation, Data curation. **Rosa Noguera:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Carmen Salguero-Aranda:** Validation, Investigation. **Daniel Delgado-Bellido:** Investigation. **Laura Romero-Pérez:** Investigation. **Uta Dirksen:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Enrique de Álava:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yexmp.2025.105008>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Biswas, B., Rastogi, S., Khan, S.A., Shukla, N.K., Deo, S.V., Agarwala, S., et al., 2015 May. Developing a prognostic model for localized Ewing sarcoma family of tumors: a single institutional experience of 224 cases treated with uniform chemotherapy protocol. *J. Surg. Oncol.* 111 (6), 683–689 (PubMed PMID: 25557999. Epub 2015/01/06).
- Bonney, M.E., Moriya, H., Amon, A., 2015 May 1. Aneuploid proliferation defects in yeast are not driven by copy number changes of a few dosage-sensitive genes. *Genes Dev.* 29 (9), 898–903 (PubMed PMID: 25934502. PMID: PMC4421978. Epub 2015/05/03).
- Bosma, S.E., Lancia, C., Rueten-Budde, A.J., Ranft, A., Gelderblom, H., Fiocco, M., et al., 2019 Jul 29. Easy-to-use clinical tool for survival estimation in Ewing sarcoma at diagnosis and after surgery. *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1), 11000 (PubMed PMID: 31358784. PMID: PMC6662666. Epub 2019/07/31).
- Brisset, S., Schleiermacher, G., Peter, M., Mairal, A., Oberlin, O., Delattre, O., et al., 2001 Oct 1. CGH analysis of secondary genetic changes in Ewing tumors: correlation with metastatic disease in a series of 43 cases. *Cancer Genet. Cytogenet.* 130 (1), 57–61 (PubMed PMID: 11672775. Epub 2001/10/24).
- Brohl, A.S., Solomon, D.A., Chang, W., Wang, J., Song, Y., Sindiri, S., et al., 2014 Jul. The genomic landscape of the Ewing sarcoma family of tumors reveals recurrent STAG2 mutation. *PLoS Genet.* 10 (7), e1004475 (PubMed PMID: 25010205. PMID: 4091782. Epub 2014/07/11. eng).
- Cidre-Aranaz, F., Watson, S., Amatruda, J.F., Nakamura, T., Delattre, O., de Alava, E., et al., 2022 Oct 6. Small round cell sarcomas. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Primers* 8 (1), 66 (PubMed PMID: 36202860. Epub 2022/10/07).

- Crompton, B.D., Stewart, C., Taylor-Weiner, A., Alexe, G., Kurek, K.C., Calicchio, M.L., et al., 2014 Nov. The genomic landscape of pediatric Ewing sarcoma. *Cancer Discov.* 4 (11), 1326–1341 (PubMed PMID: 25186949. Epub 2014/09/05. eng).
- Davoli, T., Xu, A.W., Mengwasser, K.E., Sack, L.M., Yoon, J.C., Park, P.J., et al., 2013 Nov 7. Cumulative haploinsufficiency and triplosensitivity drive aneuploidy patterns and shape the cancer genome. *Cell* 155 (4), 948–962 (PubMed PMID: 24183448. PMID: PMC3891052. Epub 2013/11/05).
- Dupuy, M., Lamoureux, F., Mullard, M., Postec, A., Regnier, L., Baud'huin, M., et al., 2023. Ewing sarcoma from molecular biology to the clinic. *Front Cell Dev. Biol.* 11, 1248753 (PubMed PMID: 37752913. PMID: PMC10518617. Epub 2023/09/27).
- Ferreira, B.I., Alonso, J., Carrillo, J., Acquadro, F., Largo, C., Suela, J., et al., 2008 Mar 27. Array CGH and gene-expression profiling reveals distinct genomic instability patterns associated with DNA repair and cell-cycle checkpoint pathways in Ewing's sarcoma. *Oncogene* 27 (14), 2084–2090 (PubMed PMID: 17952124. Epub 2007/10/24).
- Girish, V., Lakhani, A.A., Thompson, S.L., Scaduto, C.M., Brown, L.M., Hagenson, R.A., et al., 2023 Aug 25. Oncogene-like addiction to aneuploidy in human cancers. *Science* 381 (6660), eadg4521 (PubMed PMID: 37410869. PMID: PMC10753973. Epub 2023/07/06).
- Gounder, M.M., Agaram, N.P., Trabucco, S.E., Robinson, V., Ferraro, R.A., Millis, S.Z., et al., 2022 Jun 15. Clinical genomic profiling in the management of patients with soft tissue and bone sarcoma. *Nat. Commun.* 13 (1), 3406 (PubMed PMID: 35705558. PMID: PMC9200814. Epub 2022/06/16).
- Grobner, S.N., Worst, B.C., Weischenfeldt, J., Buchhalter, I., Kleinheinz, K., Rudneva, V. A., et al., 2018 Mar 15. The landscape of genomic alterations across childhood cancers. *Nature* 555 (7696), 321–327 (PubMed PMID: 29489754. Epub 2018/03/01).
- Grunevald, T.G.P., Cidre-Aranaz, F., Surdez, D., Tomazou, E.M., de Alava, E., Kovar, H., et al., 2018. Ewing sarcoma. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Primers.* 4 (1), 5. PubMed PMID: 29977059. Epub 2018/07/07.
- Hanahan, D., Weinberg, R.A., 2011 Mar 4. Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation. *Cell* 144 (5), 646–674 (PubMed PMID: 21376230. Epub 2011/03/08).
- Hattinger, C.M., Rumpel, S., Ambros, I.M., Strehl, S., Lion, T., Zoubek, A., et al., 1996 Nov. Demonstration of the translocation der(16)t(1;16)(q12;q11.2) in interphase nuclei of Ewing tumors. *Genes Chromosom. Cancer* 17 (3), 141–150 (PubMed PMID: 8946192. Epub 1996/11/01).
- Hattinger, C.M., Potschger, U., Tarkkanen, M., Squire, J., Zielenska, M., Kiuru-Kuhlefelt, S., et al., 2002 Jun 5. Prognostic impact of chromosomal aberrations in Ewing tumours. *Br. J. Cancer* 86 (11), 1763–1769 (PubMed PMID: 12087464. PMID: PMC2375399. Epub 2002/06/28).
- Huang, H.Y., Illei, P.B., Zhao, Z., Mazumdar, M., Huvos, A.G., Healey, J.H., et al., 2005 Jan 20. Ewing sarcomas with p53 mutation or p16/p14ARF homozygous deletion: a highly lethal subset associated with poor chemoresponse. *J. Clin. Oncol.* 23 (3), 548–558 (PubMed PMID: 15659501. Epub 2005/01/22).
- Jahromi, M.S., Putnam, A.R., Druzgal, C., Wright, J., Spraker-Perlman, H., Kinsey, M., et al., 2012 Jul-Aug. Molecular inversion probe analysis detects novel copy number alterations in Ewing sarcoma. *Cancer Gene Ther.* 205 (7–8), 391–404 (PubMed PMID: 22868000. PMID: PMC3784316. Epub 2012/08/08).
- Kallen, M.E., Hornick, J.L., 2021 Jan. The 2020 WHO classification: what's new in soft tissue tumor pathology? *Am. J. Surg. Pathol.* 45 (1), e1–e23 (PubMed PMID: 32796172. Epub 2020/08/17).
- Karski, E.E., McIlvaine, E., Segal, M.R., Krailo, M., Grier, H.E., Granowetter, L., et al., 2016 Jan. Identification of discrete prognostic groups in Ewing sarcoma. *Pediatr. Blood Cancer* 63 (1), 47–53 (PubMed PMID: 26257296. PMID: PMC5011751. Epub 2015/08/11).
- Kovar, H., Pospisilova, S., Jug, G., Printz, D., Gadner, H., 2003 May 22. Response of Ewing tumor cells to forced and activated p53 expression. *Oncogene* 22 (21), 3193–3204 (PubMed PMID: 12761489. Epub 2003/05/23).
- Mackintosh, C., Ordonez, J.L., Garcia-Dominguez, D.J., Sevillano, V., Llombart-Bosch, A., Szuhai, K., et al., 2012 Mar 8. 1q gain and CDT2 overexpression underlie an aggressive and highly proliferative form of Ewing sarcoma. *Oncogene* 31 (10), 1287–1298 (PubMed PMID: 21822310. Epub 2011/08/09. eng).
- Nacev, B.A., Sanchez-Vega, F., Smith, S.A., Antonescu, C.R., Rosenbaum, E., Shi, H., et al., 2022 Jun 15. Clinical sequencing of soft tissue and bone sarcomas delineates diverse genomic landscapes and potential therapeutic targets. *Nat. Commun.* 13 (1), 3405 (PubMed PMID: 35705560. PMID: PMC9200818. Epub 2022/06/16).
- Olmedo-Pelayo, J., Granado-Calle, E., Delgado-Bellido, D., Lobo-Selma, L., Jordan-Perez, C., Monteiro-Amaral, A.T., et al., 2025 Oct. EWS::FLI1-DHX9 interaction promotes Ewing sarcoma sensitivity to DNA topoisomerase 1 poisons by altering R-loop metabolism. *Oncogene* 44 (38), 3537–3552 (PubMed PMID: 40721661. PMID: PMC12436182. Epub 2025/07/29).
- Ordonez, J.L., Amaral, A.T., Carcaboso, A.M., Herrero-Martin, D., del Carmen, Garcia-Macias M., Sevillano, V., et al., 2015 Aug 7. The PARP inhibitor olaparib enhances the sensitivity of Ewing sarcoma to trabectedin. *Oncotarget* 6 (22), 18875–18890 (PubMed PMID: 26056084. PMID: PMC4662461. Epub 2015/06/10).
- Ozaki, T., Paulussen, M., Poremba, C., Brinkschmidt, C., Rerim, J., Ahrens, S., et al., 2001 Oct. Genetic imbalances revealed by comparative genomic hybridization in Ewing tumors. *Genes Chromosom. Cancer* 32 (2), 164–171 (PubMed PMID: 11550284. Epub 2001/09/11).
- Piqueras, M., Navarro, S., Canete, A., Castel, V., Noguera, R., 2011 Jun 28. How to minimise the effect of tumour cell content in detection of aberrant genetic markers in neuroblastoma. *Br. J. Cancer* 105 (1), 89–92 (PubMed PMID: 21654680. PMID: PMC3137406. Epub 2011/06/10).
- Roberts, P., Burchill, S.A., Brownhill, S., Cullinane, C.J., Johnston, C., Griffiths, M.J., et al., 2008 Mar. Ploidy and karyotype complexity are powerful prognostic indicators in the Ewing's sarcoma family of tumors: a study by the United Kingdom Cancer cytogenetics and the children's Cancer and Leukaemia group. *Genes Chromosom. Cancer* 47 (3), 207–220 (PubMed PMID: 18064647. Epub 2007/12/08).
- Rodriguez-Galindo, C., Liu, T., Krasin, M.J., Wu, J., Billups, C.A., Daw, N.C., et al., 2007 Jul 15. Analysis of prognostic factors in Ewing sarcoma family of tumors: review of St. Jude Children's Research Hospital studies. *Cancer* 110 (2), 375–384 (PubMed PMID: 17569105. Epub 2007/06/15).
- Rodriguez-Nunez, P., Romero-Perez, L., Amaral, A.T., Puerto-Camacho, P., Jordan, C., Marcilla, D., et al., 2020 Apr. Hippo pathway effectors YAP1/TAZ induce an EWS-FLI1-opposing gene signature and associate with disease progression in Ewing sarcoma. *J. Pathol.* 250 (4), 374–386. PubMed PMID: 31880317. (Epub 2019/12/28. eng).
- Salguero-Aranda, C., Diaz-Martín, J., 2021. Molecular approaches to diagnosis in Ewing sarcoma: targeted RNA sequencing. *Methods Mol. Biol.* 2226, 105–116 (PubMed PMID: 33326096. Epub 2020/12/17).
- Salguero-Aranda, C., Amaral, A.T., Olmedo-Pelayo, J., Diaz-Martín, J., Alava, E., 2020 Mar 26. Breakthrough technologies reshape the Ewing sarcoma molecular landscape. *Cells* 9 (4) (PubMed PMID: 32225029. PMID: PMC7226764. Epub 2020/04/01).
- Savola, S., Klami, A., Tripathi, A., Niini, T., Serra, M., Picci, P., et al., 2009 Jan. Combined use of expression and CGH arrays pinpoints novel candidate genes in Ewing sarcoma family of tumors. *BMC Cancer* 14 (9), 17 (PubMed PMID: 19144156. PMID: PMC2633345. Epub 2009/01/16).
- Shulman, D.S., Whittle, S.B., Surdez, D., Bailey, K.M., de Alava, E., Yustein, J.T., et al., 2022 Sep 17. An international working group consensus report for the prioritization of molecular biomarkers for Ewing sarcoma. *NPJ Precis Oncol.* 6 (1), 65 (PubMed PMID: 36115869. PMID: PMC9482616. Epub 2022/09/18).
- Shulman, D.S., Chen, S., Hall, D., Nag, A., Thorner, A.R., Lessnick, S.L., et al., 2022 Dec. Adverse prognostic impact of the loss of STAG2 protein expression in patients with newly diagnosed localised Ewing sarcoma: a report from the children's oncology group. *Br. J. Cancer* 127 (12), 2220–2226 (PubMed PMID: 36221002. PMID: PMC9726932. Epub 2022/10/12).
- Stahl, M., Ranft, A., Paulussen, M., Bolling, T., Vieth, V., Bielack, S., et al., 2011 Oct. Risk of recurrence and survival after relapse in patients with Ewing sarcoma. *Pediatr. Blood Cancer* 57 (4), 549–553 (PubMed PMID: 21442722. Epub 2011/03/29).
- Taluri, S., Oza, V.H., Soelter, T.M., Fisher, J.L., Lasseigne, B.N., 2023 Dec. Inferring chromosomal instability from copy number aberrations as a measure of chromosomal instability across human cancers. *Cancer Rep (Hoboken)* 6 (12) e1902. PubMed PMID: 37680168. PMID: PMC10728508. (Epub 2023/09/08).
- Tijhuis, A.E., Johnson, S.C., McClelland, S.E., 2019 May. The emerging links between chromosomal instability (CIN), metastasis, inflammation and tumour immunity. *Mol. Cytogenet.* 14 (12), 17 (PubMed PMID: 31114634. PMID: PMC6518824. interests.Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Epub 2019/05/23).
- Tirole, F., Surdez, D., Ma, X., Parker, M., Le Deley, M.C., Bahrami, A., et al., 2014 Nov. Genomic landscape of Ewing sarcoma defines an aggressive subtype with co-association of STAG2 and TP53 mutations. *Cancer Discov.* 4 (11), 1342–1353 (PubMed PMID: 25223734. PMID: 4264969. Epub 2014/09/17. eng).
- WHO Classification of Tumours Editorial Board, 2020. WHO Classification of Tumours of Soft Tissue and Bone, 5th ed. IARC Press, Lyon, France.
- Zielenska, M., Zhang, Z.M., Ng, K., Marrano, P., Bayani, J., Ramirez, O.C., et al., 2001 Jun 1. Acquisition of secondary structural chromosomal changes in pediatric Ewing sarcoma is a probable prognostic factor for tumor response and clinical outcome. *Cancer* 91 (11), 2156–2164 (PubMed PMID: 11391597. Epub 2001/06/08).